

Providing and developing basic programs to enhance and raise productivity

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Abstract

The construct of productivity has evolved over and within the past centuries, especially during current decades, and is deemed by all scholars as a factor determining the level of individual, organizational and national life. Various indicators are at play in raising productivity, identifying and prioritizing them in any organization is a crucial step to enhance the productivity.

For determining a principled program to raise the productivity, numerous methods can be deployed, in this vein; the requirement is to deploy a suitable tool to find an efficient and effective solution to enhance the productivity. In this respect, operational research tools are one of the most efficient tools for optimal allocation of resources due to the fact that the productivity accentuates this important issue as well. This article hypothesized that productivity programs have to be comprehensive, continuous, with the participation of the employees, with quantitative indicators, beside information and evaluation system in order to enhance and raise the productivity.

Keywords: Productivity, Basic Plans, Organization and Workforce.

INTRODUCTION

Establishing the ground and paving the way for cultural growth, national power, prosperity and public welfare prerequisites the proper economic functioning of the country. Economic growth also is reliant on the amount of production and competition in global markets. Via improving productivity, it is feasible to provide better services at a lower cost, where it is possible to compete in global markets. So, focusing on the productivity is inevitable for the survival and development of the activities of an institution or the economic growth and development of a nation. Economic progress is achieved in line with the national and regional advantages and thinking power of the human resource of each country. Apparatus, equipment, and even technical knowledge and methods of operation are tools in the hands of human beings that are used to achieve goals, and only intelligence in activities, which is synonymous with the attitude of productivity, directs activities. And makes the performance of systems and collections valuable and credible. The competitive world today is focused on productivity and that is more productive and will be more successful. Productivity is one of the concepts of economics and means maximizing profits by optimally using resources to improve society.

Iran has been a member of the Asian Productivity Organization since its establishment until the Islamic Revolution in February 1978. Iran's membership was suspended in 1979. Since 1984, with the approval of the Islamic Consultative Assembly, it has rejoined the organization. Then, the National Productivity Organization of Iran was established in 1985 under the Ministry of Heavy Industries. The National Productivity Organization later joined the Ministry of Industry and in 1998 the Employment Affairs Organization and has mostly sought cultural work in spreading and promoting a culture of productivity at various levels of society.

Strategies to raise the productivity require sufficient knowledge of the current situation and work culture of companies. Considering the important differences in the work culture of companies and their current situation, it can be said that strategies to increase productivity will also be different in them. Among the strategies to increase productivity, we can mention waste reduction, creating commitment in employees, paying attention to employees, optimal use of

talents, motivating employees, paying attention to changes, and so on. The degree of effectiveness of each of these strategies in increasing productivity depends on the current situation of the company in that field and the need to address each of these issues, which must be skillfully identified and prioritized and acted upon.

Theoretical Framework

In this part of the paper, we will review the theoretical approaches to the issue of improving and enhancing productivity. The framework for presenting the content is that we will first discuss (productivity). In the continuation of the research, the effective factors on productivity promotion are examined.

Productivity is one of the most significant variables affecting economic activities. A relatively easy and basic review of the literature reveals that those who use productivity rarely define it, and it should be noted that decisions to enhance productivity are often based on personal opinions rather than a common view and is carried out publicly (Moshfeghi, 2012). Productivity is the product of dividing the production value or value added of an economic activity by the costs used to gain that amount of production or value added over a given period of time. (Taheri, Shahnam, 2009: 110)

Table 1-2: some of the definitions of productivity

Rows	Definitions	Purposers
1	Division of labor is a major factor in increasing productivity	Adam Smith 1776
2	Productivity is the ability to produce	Litre 1883
3	Productivity is the fraction obtained by dividing the quantity or value of a product by the quantity or value of one of the factors of production.	Oeec, 1953
4	Changes in the amount of product due to the resources used	rr1995T
5	Productivity is the degree of effective use of each of the factors of production	Epa, 1958
6	The ratio of output to input is called efficiency	,Fabricant 1962
7	Productivity is used to show the ratio of output to input within an individual, unit or organization.	Johnson 1984
8	Productivity: Number of outputs / number of inputs.	Cho, 1988
9	Productivity: Actual output / resources expected to be used.	Sink and Tuttle, 1986
10	Productivity is what men can achieve with raw materials, capital and technology. It is basically an individual behavior. It is an attitude that we must constantly improve ourselves and what is around us	Japan Productivity Center Quoted from Beechurken 1991

Table of resources (Saatchi, 2009)

In contrast to pervasive belief, productivity is not just for industries, but productivity has many levels and layers, and everyone has a role to play at all levels, i.e. people can be effective from practically various levels with their thinking, innovation, and innovation. Different levels of productivity are:

Individual level, house level, group level, organizational level, level of business, service, industrial or agricultural fields, level of economic sectors and national level (Vere, 2009).

Enhancing productivity in the organization is the outcome of efficient and effective management and use of resources, reducing waste, reducing cost, improving the quality of improving customer satisfaction, pleasantness in the workplace and increasing employee motivation and interest in better work, which ultimately leads to growth and development of the organization. Be. Organizational productivity is often defined in relation to productivity and individuals (Berger & Master, 2010).

There exist different views on productivity, some of which have been identified with respect to productivity. Some of them are: systemic perspective, quality perspective (Japanese): economic approach, managerial perspective, awareness, responsibility, productivity as a goal. Multi-factor perspective, improving technique and productivity as a building (Berger & Master, 2010).

A system is a set of factors that interact to achieve goals in such a way that data or data enters the system. After a process and change and conversion, it is output. While it is the ratio of output to data. Therefore, it can be seen that productivity and systems theory are closely related. In order to clarify what role productivity plays in a system, the subject is described. Productivity can be targeted as well as system feedback. If targeted by a system, the system is considered as an organization of higher production and service delivery or productivity, as many of these organizations that aim to increase their long-term profits, one of the They formulate hypotheses and, in fact, the most important ground for increase in increasing productivity (Yousefi, 2011). The most important role that productivity can play in a system. The role is the feedback of the system. A dynamic system continuously compares its outputs with the data spent on that output or measures its productivity, constantly striving to improve productivity.

Planning and development of industrial productivity is a feedback to be used in planning and preparation. This feedback has the following characteristics:

1. If the organization has a formal productivity management and engineering system, the productivity feedback is formal, but if it deploys productivity informally has informal feedback.
2. The feedback of productivity may be hump. This feedback is produced when the system productivity falls lower than certain and expected level, and actually the productivity feedback is part of the management system based on exceptions. In the management system, according to the exception of managers, they set specific criteria and objectives for the organization. Only if they digress from these criteria and goals, they design and implement programs to hinder this flow i.e. deviation from the specified, defined and intended objectives of the managers (Capalo & Danny, 2008).

Productivity feedback can be founded in all natural and manual systems, permanent and transient, compatible and incongruous, machine and human, and generally systems hierarchies, from inanimate systems to excellent living systems, have efficiency feedback. They have the characteristics below;

1. These systems are ideal. Otherwise stated, they can act in different ways in order to obtain a specific goal that is ultimately to develop and enhance productivity.
2. Subsystems; this system also has a productivity feedback loop. For instance, a business organization that has productivity feedback, productivity feedback in all sub-units of the company, comprises production, purchasing, sales, office units. And also not to be forgotten to be mentioned, there is finance.
3. The more orderly the systems are, in better terminology, the better they move towards growth and development, and they will also be more productive. (Capalo and Danny, 2008).

Productivity is a national and pervasive issue in Japan, and as a historical approach, the strategy of improving productivity along with total quality control (TQC) and total quality management (TQM) is proposed. They see

productivity as an ongoing process that must be constantly improved and state three principles for improvement that are mentioned as;

- 1) Staff development
- 2) Participatory management
- 3) Fair distribution of productivity growth (Mansouri, 2009)

In terms of economy, the amount of output or output is assumed to be a function of capital and labor factors. Therefore, increasing the skills of the workforce or changes in technology or boosting skills along with improvement and technology can raise the amount of production and move the production function upwards to increase productivity. All in all, nowadays productivity is an economic, technical and cultural attitude towards production in which human beings perform their activities intelligently and tactfully to gain the best outcomes at the lowest cost in less time. Regardless of the fact that productivity has been outlined more classically in economic matters, the concept of productivity can be deemed in any matter of daily life up to the countless cycles of industry (Berger & Master, 2010).

The managerial perspective points to the tasks of senior management as the most significant factor influencing the increase of productivity that factors such as resource mobilization, facilities can be effective that can conclude to optimization of the resources. (Mansouri, 2009).

Organizational awareness perspective includes the participation and understanding of all individuals and organizational systems in productivity and takes into the account raising productivity to be feasible when all people understand it and take steps towards it (Mansouri, 2009).

In the continuation of the view, organizational awareness states that in addition to understanding the need for productivity, it should feel responsible for it, and this sense of responsibility should be present in all organizational individuals or a country (Capallo, 2011).

The main goal of the organization is not only profitability or customer satisfaction but also productivity is a strategic and programmable goal for the long term in the organization.

The technique improvement perspective focuses on the process and the path in addition to the inputs, and sees an increase in productivity when techniques for producing goods or providing services are improved. Compares the necessary components for productivity to the components or elements of an organization that the absence or defect of one can affect the overall quality of the building (Moshfeghi, 2012).

In the multifactorial perspective of productivity, it is said that an organization will reach the desired and optimal level in a situation that all factors inside and outside the organization affect the individual and job productivity of employees, as well as different organs of a living being harmonious, aligned and effective To act. The related model is a systematic model of selecting and using effective human resources in the organization: in a situation, an ideal person or idea is valuable from a practical point of view and can predict the possibility of reducing or increasing personal, job and productivity. An organization that pays

- 1) Identify all human factors and barriers affecting organizational productivity (Capallo, 2011).
- 2) Classify the indicators.
- 3) The interrelationships of each of these factors with each other
- 4) Exhibits the specific position of each factor in the model designed for this goal (Christensen, 2005).

People often consider that if efficiency improves, productivity will increase. Efficiency is a necessary condition for productivity, but it is not a sufficient condition. In fact, in order to be productive, both effectiveness and efficiency need to be the ratio of the actual product produced to the expected product (standard). While effectiveness is the degree of achievement of goals in the organization.

If a company's revenue increases, it does not mean that the company is highly productive. Essentially every company in the world sets sales revenue targets that they discuss on a daily, weekly and monthly basis. Though, they control less the amount of productivity and the organization and this may increase its revenues for some reasons (for example, price raise). Due to the existence of a monopoly market, while its productivity has not increased compared to before, in the future its profitability will increase sharply (Ansari et al., 2011).

Theoretical Background of the study

Ansari Renani Ghasem, Sabzi Aliabadi Sara (2011) Prioritization of organizational indicators influencing the promotion of human resource productivity in small industries: The importance of small industries in the economic development of countries, has led to increasing attention of policymakers in different societies. Since the most essential factor or lever of reducing or increasing the productivity of the organization is its human resources, so one of the issues that will involve the managers of leading organizations in the coming decades is trying to increase the job productivity of employees. Hence, in the paper, first the factors affecting the promotion of human resource productivity through studying

the models presented in this field and interviewing experts, were identified and then prioritizing organizational factors affecting the improvement of human resource productivity through testing Friedman has done. Finally, the finalized model is obtained using the test results.

Moshfeghi, Somayeh, 2012, has a reaserch on a Effective Factors in Increasing Manpower Productivity: Efforts to Improve and Use Effectively and Efficiently from Various Resources such as Labor, Capital, Materials, Energy and Information. The result shows the purpose of all Managers of Economic Organizations and Industrial Production Units and Service Organizations.

Ghabdezi (2013) in a study entitled as” Factors affecting the productivity of human resources in research centers (Case study: Petroleum Industry Research Institute)” concluded that leadership methods, training, payment system, organizational structure and selection and recruitment correctly affect the productivity of human capital in the Petroleum Industry Research Institute.

Ala Al-Molki et al. (2004) in a study on cognition and comparison of ways to increase the productivity of human resources in Semnan University of Medical Sciences and Health Services while conducting a descriptive-inferential study on 200 people. Identify material factors of motivation, training and organizational structure to increase productivity.

Tabibi and Baghbanian (2006) in their research, while examining the factors affecting the productivity of human resources in the hospitals of Shiraz University of Medical Sciences, acknowledged that productivity is not only a function of individual characteristics, but also of the organization and environment.

The results of Nairi (2009) and Hejazi (2008) studies also indicate that effective evaluation can increase productivity and the more training the workforce benefits, the better the quality of human resources and consequently increasing the amount of production will have more.

Mirzaei, Behnam (2012) in a study entitled Factors affecting the improvement of human resource productivity in the Industry, Mining and Trade Organization of Tehran Province, human resource management concluded that there is a significant relationship between all organizational factors (including: participation, selection There is the right staff, payment system, leadership practices, organizational structure and training programs) with the productivity of human resources, which has the greatest impact on employee participation in productivity.

Najaflavi Turkmani in a study entitled "Study of the relationship between employees 'awareness of the goals of the organization and their efficiency" has stated that employees' awareness of the goals of the organization increases the possibility of creativity and innovation to achieve the goals of the organization.

Sadeghi (2012) in a study entitled as” Factors affecting the productivity of human resources of the central headquarters of the Welfare Organization concluded that manpower training” found that it had the greatest impact on increasing the productivity of the organization.

Ghasemi (2011) in a study entitled Internal Organizational Manpower Factors in the Post Company of the Islamic Republic of Iran stated that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational structure and human resource productivity with the first priority among other factors.

In their research in China, Wright et al. (2011) evaluated the role of the organizational culture element in increasing employee motivation as well as improving effective productivity.

Some research has examined the relationship between intellectual capital components and traditional measures of firm performance (productivity and market valuation) in the Indian pharmaceutical industry. Analyzes showed that human capital has an important effect on the profitability and productivity of companies during the study period (Kams, 2008).

The results of some Indian researchers showed that the relationship between the company's intellectual capital performance and traditional performance indicators (profitability, productivity and market valuation) is different. The performance of corporate intellectual capital can explain productivity but cannot explain productivity and market valuation in India (Qosh and Mandel, 2009).

Ellis and Dick (2003) in their research concluded that the use of participatory leadership style for group work improves productivity. In Kim (2009) research, the effect of information and communication technology on labor productivity has been evaluated as positive and significant.

Employees only when they have a good opportunity to participate and take responsibility for set goals. They will seriously pursue and ensure productivity growth. When employees take responsibility for productivity goals, they will also be held accountable, and it is necessary to have a control and monitoring system in place to guide employees in their responsibilities and Provide and develop basic programs to improve and increase productivity (Belcher, 2000).

It should always be noted and kept in mind that multidimensional factors influence the productivity of an organization that can be generally divided into two categories of factors within the organization and outside the organization. External factors are factors that the management of the institution is not able to control or influence in the short term, which are:

- 1) Business cycle including economic, demographic changes, Environmental, social;
- 2) Resources including manpower, Earth and energy;
- 3) Government and its policies.

Intra-organizational factors that are under the control of organizational management and include three categories of input factors, process factors and output factors (input, process, output and feedback) (Divert, 2007).

Factors affecting the productivity of organizations

Business cycle and structural changes	Sources	Policy
Sectorial structural changes	Manpower	Structure analysis policies
Business conditions	Supply	Productivity policies
Structural changes	Demand	Business cycle policies
Fund	Education	Environmental laws
Scale savings	flexibility	financial and monetary policies
Demographic change	Dynamics and mobility the earth	Education and training of human resources
Social change	accessibility	
	Value	
	Materials and energy	
	Access to financial resource	

Intra-organizational

Input factors	Process factors	Output factors
Capital, workshop, equipment	Manpower; Motivation Education, career history, industrial relations	Volume
Materials and energy	product design	Product composition
Technology and technical knowledge	Technology	Quality
product design	Operation of factory and equipment	Innovation in product design and packaging services
Manpower, selection and employment	Change, maintenance and development	after sales service
	Materials and energy	Timely delivery
	Working methods	Product accessibility
	Feedback; Analysis measurement	Technical system and commitment
	Organizational systems and management practices	Market penetration and share
		Mental image of the organization

Dr. Rezaian in his book Management of Organizational Behavior has shown the factors affecting organizational productivity in the form of a satellite model. In this model, important factors have been identified that include organizational structure, knowledge, non-human resources, strategic position and human processes. In examining organizational structure, type of organization, various management systems, information systems and flexibility of the organization are considered. And knowledge necessary for organizational productivity includes technical knowledge, administrative, human process and system knowledge.

In the study of non-human resources, equipment, workshops, work environment, type of technology, amount of investment and liquidity are discussed. The strategic position of the organization is the type of its activities and the markets in which it has a share.

Social policies shape the organization's manpower and environmental changes, and ultimately human processes mean the values that govern individuals and groups, attitudes, norms, and interactions between them. The combination of these factors is not only necessary to achieve the current goals of the organization and social needs, but also the process of change in order to achieve the goals and future needs of the organization (Taheri, 2010).

While all of these factors are important, the source of the organization's productive movements lies in human resources. For this reason, the Japanese believe that productivity is not only the ratio of output to input but also includes human elements and variables and consider human resources as the main factor in Japan's progress (Moshfeghi, 2012).

(Moshfeghi, 2012)

External or uncontrollable factors or external factors refer to factors that affect the organization from the outside and are not under the control of individuals and managers within the organization. That is, the management of the organization is not able to control or influence them in the short term. Inevitably, the organization must adapt to their changes. Such as national laws and regulations of international policies, tax regulations and laws, economic, political, social factors and relations, etc.

Internal or controllable factors or factors within the organization. These factors are under the scope and authority of individuals and managers within the organization that can be used with high efficiency with proper reflection and management. These factors can be divided as follows:

Hardware factors: such as machinery and equipment, and technology, raw materials, energy, tools, financial resources, land (Sadeghi, 2012).

Software factors: such as information, instructions, maps and formulas.

Human or brain-enhancing factors: These factors are divided into two main characteristics:

A: Factors affecting the improvement of human resource productivity like the Technical and specialized ability of the workforce and the power to do work such as science, and experience, education, personality and talent, etc.

Motivation and willingness to do work such as material needs, physical needs, psychological needs, work environment, management attitudes towards motivation and so on.

B) Factors affecting the promotion of management productivity such as:

Philosophy and style of management

Organize, plan, coordinate and control.

Information Systems Management. (Yousefi, 2012).

Dimensions of productivity are:

1- Working methods:

Transfer and replacement of manpower

The tool to be used. Places that are selected for production and etc. are all methods of work. Methods of work by systematic analysis of existing methods, eliminating unnecessary work and doing more necessary work with less effort and less cost (Khaki, 2008).

2- Efficiency:

3- Decision quality:

The better the decisions made based on the available information.

4- Joint participation and influence:

The degree to which conjectures within an organization are involved in making decisions that directly affect their work and destiny (Divert, 2007).

5- Quality of information analysis:

Faster analysis of information and data and preparation of timely reports on the use of office automation.

6- Quality of products or services:

The quality of major products or services provided by humans may take many practical forms, which is determined by the type of products and services provided by the organization and customer responsiveness (Christensen, 2005).

One of the effective factors in increasing productivity is hiring and retaining the employees who have the highest efficiency for your organization. Company managers and human resource management are better to hire employees who are efficient, creative and have high learning power. Then, with proper management and leadership, strategic planning, setting business goals and establishing job satisfaction, increase employee productivity in the organization.

1- Increase efficiency with key methods

To increase productivity, the first step is to look at how your organization's jobs are performing, and if there is a need to change the method in the organization, determine how to change the method. Make short-term and long-term to-do lists and improve productivity by prioritizing tasks.

What better way than to have employees set specific goals each day and structure their day? Encourage each employee to make a to-do list and make sure they prioritize and do things correctly and stay up all day and see that the results are more efficient.

2- Leave the leadership of the team to the employees

If you increase the responsibility of your staff, their job satisfaction will increase and their morale will improve. Assign and trust qualified employees who have a track record of success in certain areas.

Giving employees the opportunity to gain leadership and representation skills and experience will benefit the company and give them a sense of accomplishment in their careers.

3- Reduce distraction

Social media and mobile phone use are a major reason for reduced productivity at work, but it is not possible to be too strict and eliminate it. So try to keep employees focused and busy while giving them time to breathe.

Our suggestion is to encourage employees to turn off their cell phones but turn them on regularly when resting, which will increase the time spent at their desk.

4- Provide appropriate tools and equipment

Providing appropriate tools and equipment to increase the productivity of the organization's employees is of great importance to perform their duties efficiently and in a timely manner and increase their productivity. For example, there is nothing worse than spending time waiting for paper printing, because your organization does not have a fast printing press.

New and high quality programs and equipment have a great impact on the workforce and the speed of their activities.

5- Adjust the work environment temperature

Ambient temperature also affects the work process and productivity of the organization's forces. Too hot or cold environment distracts employees and forces spend more time adjusting the temperature of heating and cooling equipment. Make sure the air conditioning systems are in working order.

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Our suggestion is to encourage employees to turn off their cell phones but turn them on regularly when resting, which will increase the time spent at their desk.

7- Provide appropriate tools and equipment

Provide the right tools and equipment to increase the productivity of the organization's employees of high importance - set organizational goals.

A common problem for most managers is that they do not have a clear understanding of whether their employees are performing well. They have not set tangible goals for their organization. Above all, it is better to determine the goals of your organization and carefully determine the role of each person in achieving these goals to see the increase in employee productivity in the organization.

8. Encourage, motivate and reward

If your forces are doing something useful, encourage them and give them feedback. Make constructive criticism. Receive incentive activities such as incentive leave or eating out in a restaurant and برای to do positive things beyond their duty.

We help to clarify the position of your employees in the organization with guidance and advice. If an employee is more successful than other employees, show it to others, by doing so you will motivate not only that person, but others as well. When you motivate your employees, it makes them work harder and more happily, and instead rewards you, thereby increasing productivity in your organization.

9- Try to make your employees happy

A work environment despite stress does not have optimistic results. If employees work in a stressful environment and are less efficient, this will lead to more absenteeism and dissatisfaction in the workplace. Try to keep your troops happy. Appreciate and respect your employees.

10- Plan to improve staff skills

After being opted and hired in the workplace, training is an essential part of ensuring and increasing productivity. Training has many advantages for both managers and employees. The smallest of these benefits is learning newer and faster ways to get things done, which also enhances your employees' skills in carrying out them.

11. If possible, attract the "remote work" force

Hiring for telecommuting is a great way to increase employee productivity in your organization. Remote employees work longer hours, take less leave, perform better, and generally work longer. In addition, all these cases cause significant savings in costs for your company (Jafari, 2020, 1-3).

Establishing the productivity cycle network is a legal task that is emphasized in Article 5 of the Sixth Development Plan and the executive bodies are obliged to put the establishment of the productivity cycle on their agenda. To this end, the executive bodies and institutions must formulate productivity promotion programs under the title of operational plans and submit them to the National Productivity Organization for approval. Our focus in the discussion of productivity deployment is to identify productivity issues, and devices should provide and implement improvement options based on this issue and the facilities at their disposal.

Given that productivity needs to be cultured, we expect the Broadcasting Organization to get involved in this issue, and if this is achieved, more tangible results will be achieved. Better performance of devices in establishing the productivity cycle does not mean that they are more productive. In productivity assessment, labor, capital and total productivity indicators are measured in devices. The agencies in charge of the economy in the sectors of oil, agriculture, mining, industry, communications, transportation, water and gas, construction and other services were divided into eight

sub-sectors and finalized their productivity improvement program, which was sent to the Cabinet to be approved by the Cabinet.

Comparison of Central Asian countries shows that we are far apart in terms of productivity and economic growth, and we must take steps faster.

We have the National Productivity Organization of Iran, which plans, policy-making, leading, monitoring and evaluating the productivity of all production factors, formulating strategic plans to improve productivity, preparing, compiling and communicating instructions on determining productivity indicators and monitoring the performance of executive bodies in performing tasks. Is responsible for the law on productivity. An organization that has been transferred many times between ministries and parent organizations and at any time, a subset of them has been until finally, since 2016, it has been affiliated with the administrative and employment organization of the country.

Unless we seek to train innovative and productive people in our education system, we cannot expect to benefit from it in the administrative system, businesses and industrial space of the country, because these people do not have the basic capabilities. Since the training of our human resources is not based on the labor market, a serious imbalance arises and the labor market does not require many of our university graduates. Unfortunately, one of the main factors affecting the reduction of productivity is not believing in the issue of productivity. Part of this belief is the lack of economic influence that we have been in for more than 50 years; That is, the oil economy. An oil-based economy makes revenue easy to access, provides current revenue directly to governments, and governments do not need to bother. This practice has also affected our culture, so that our consumption has been smooth and achievable. Our textbooks also do not teach students that you have to work, think, come up with solutions, and choose the right methods to produce and live a better life. At least 12 years ago, in the fourth to sixth development plans, productivity was considered and it was clearly stated that in the fourth plan, one-third and in the next two plans, up to 35% of economic growth should be achieved from the place of productivity. But the government affects a large part of the economy and does not have a sound productivity strategy. There are only a series of recommendations, a master plan and an outline, and the necessary capacity building has not been done on how we should work on a productivity basis. Evaluations are also not based on productivity. The payroll system, which covers a large part of society. It operates not on the basis of efficiency and productivity, but on the basis of attendance. The one who comes from the beginning and works with motivation and the one who comes very reluctantly and is the burden of that set, both receive their salaries at the end of the month and are no different. The evaluations we make for rewards are all formal. Our administrative system and appointments are not designed based on productivity. When we are going to appoint a senior manager for a position, consider that we have several criteria for choosing a manager, and from the candidates, we choose the one who has the highest score, regardless of affiliation with a political thought and current (Sheriff, 2019: 11-10).

Unfortunately, this culture has spread to some extent in our private sector as well. Lack of belief, strategy, appointment system, meritocracy and efficiency-based payment system go hand in hand so that productivity does not reach its desired level. In the current administrative system, an employee feels that his innovation is not much different and therefore does not receive significant rewards. Even sometimes, people who are brave and courageous are interrogated and prosecuted by regulatory and inspection organizations, because doing something new has consequences and he must be held accountable. As a result, people prefer not to do innovative work and just get paid. "Narrow water" is a very bad word for government employees. We do not have a productive spirit and mind.

The National Productivity Organization has a series of governing tasks, including policy-making, planning, monitoring and coordination of the national productivity movement. It includes both the economic dimension and the administrative system. The fact that the National Productivity Organization is under the administrative and employment organization is an opportunity in one sense, because we are at the heart of the administrative system and we have the opportunity to interact more with the devices. Of course, it may create the mentality from the outside towards the organization that this organization should not enter the economic dimension.

There are several elements to improve the business environment, one of which is rules and regulations. Many of the rules and regulations that are set for the various affairs of the executive apparatus are contrary to the efficiency of the business environment. However, efforts are being made to improve the business environment. The consequences of decisions are not weighed, and we do not simulate what they are supposed to do for us. Another issue is the systems, procedures, and inter-organizational communications that we have tried to address in many ways through e-government. Like setting up counters, facilitating processes, and reducing permissions. Perhaps it can be said that due to the existing rent space, every time we have improved, there are margins next to it that also reduce the effectiveness.

Other programs that can be offered to increase productivity; Productivity management. That means you maintain the current efficiency and effectiveness of the organization. Then make plans to increase productivity. Some managers make big mistakes in the productivity management process. When their productivity in the organization increases a little, they are happy and consider it established. For this reason, they abandon their new achievement and turn to new ways to increase productivity.

Ideation for productivity management in the organization is a good job that the organization needs. But at the same time, you must be careful to maintain the quality and quantity of work at the moment. Maintaining current achievements is as important as trying to gain new benefits. By observing the following points, the best program can be presented to increase the productivity of the organization:

- Build a culture of productivity in your organization.
- It is better to link productivity goals with personal goals of your human resources. In this case, they will be interested in the process of increasing productivity and will strive for it.
- First create the structures needed to increase productivity and then move on to implementing your plans.
- Be sure to review the plans you have for managing productivity in the organization.

One of the most important programs to increase productivity is process reengineering. For this purpose, in the twenty-three strategies of the national media horizon, the second strategy is dedicated to "reviewing and modifying the process of production, supply and distribution of programs in line with the message management system", one of the four parts of which is "re-engineering the program supply process" Is. In this regard, in any organization, one of the basic programs to increase productivity is process reengineering (Sidi & Goodarzi, 2013: 56).

Other basic programs for increasing productivity include regular and accurate programs for delegating authority. Many managers encounter problems in delegating authority. These managers are either reluctant to delegate or unable to do so. Because if tasks are not delegated, the manager must do them himself, managers who do not delegate, ultimately with a lot of work and responsibility. They will face that they have to do it alone and therefore cannot use all their potential abilities for the development of the organization (Tracy, 2019: 54).

RESULT

The activities of any organization are affected by a set of factors. Identifying and examining these factors can effectively help improve activities and research organizational goals. One of the important goals of any organization is to improve quality, and especially in a competitive environment, organizations should consider improving quality by increasing productivity.

Findings of the article indicate that the importance of human creative force and equipping management with human relations and scientific findings in the field of organizational behavior and the optimal use of thinking power and individual skills of employees to achieve its goals Succeeds and if management cannot improve the motivation of the organization's skilled and skilled manpower, improve its ability to achieve organizational goals with appropriate evaluation and feedback, do not make work-appropriate decisions will be unsuccessful in improving the productivity of the organization. . Environmental factors that are effective in improving the productivity of people are other factors that the leadership of the organization must respond to them with appropriate contingent decisions so that not only the organization does not have problems in achieving its goals but also the effectiveness of the organization is maximized.

Productivity is a culture before it can be considered as an economic indicator or a factor of development. In order for productivity to take root in a society and take root in the context of indigenous beliefs and traditions, it must be seen not only as a mere economic criterion, but also as an idea. To be productive, we must believe and believe that today, we can do better than yesterday and tomorrow better than today, and this is the command of Imam Ali (AS) who says: Whoever is the same for two days is lost Is.

Productivity improvements do not happen miraculously and must be planned for. As the findings of the article show, it is necessary to give all employees the opportunity to participate in programs designed by managers. An environment must be created that creates an atmosphere of intimacy and cooperation. They should be encouraged to comment on better ways of doing things. The organization should also create opportunities for people to receive the training they need. The ability of a worker or temporary employee to find a new job depends largely on his or her skills. If a worker or employee can learn skills (for the future) in what they do, then there will be a lot of motivation for them in that job.

Therefore, due to the enormous speed of changes in technology, management and service delivery in the world today, all production and service organizations need continuous improvement and coordination with these developments. In the meantime, paying attention to productivity and presenting principled programs is one of the important and efficient solutions and infrastructure for continuous improvement in the organization, which increases the productivity of the organization in all dimensions.

Productivity is the share of management in the economy of this country. In order for a manager to have a positive valuation in the country's economy, he must master it. Unfortunately, this belief does not exist now. As a result, in the field of technology, we cannot have the right operation; we cannot define the right training and etc. This belief needs to be formed in our managers' mind from top to bottom.

- Productivity programs should be comprehensive and include the whole organization.

- Increasing productivity should be a continuous program.
- Productivity enhancement programs should be supported by senior managers.
- Do not forget about employee participation in productivity programs.
- Determining quantitative indicators for each organizational unit should be included in the program.
- Support for the implementation of productivity enhancement programs should be attracted in the organization.
- Establish an information system to present the progress of the productivity increase program.
- The evaluation and reward system of the organization should be in line with the productivity programs of the organization.
- Productivity measurement should be done in a certain period of time.
- Training managers and officials in obtaining management plans, as well as using the opinions and suggestions of employees and to provide a favorable environment for enriching and encouraging them to participate in decisions.
- Continuous training of employees can decisively contribute to economic-cultural development, social progress, organizational improvement and the development of administrative systems, so by providing more facilities and facilities can be important steps in this area.
- Paying attention to individual differences in behavior, division of labor and giving responsibilities should be noted that people have different personalities and motivations. The degree of responsibility of people is different, some people feel more satisfied with having a lot of responsibility, and instead some people do not take responsibility under the burden. People should be hired based on their talents and interests in the relevant job. This is done through selection and interview.
- The work environment should be such that the worker is not mentally and physically concerned.
- Implementation of short-term training courses within the organization to improve the level of knowledge and awareness of managers with new developments and office technologies.
- Managers must identify the strengths and weaknesses of individuals, so that they can fairly consider rewards and punishments. But this does not mean that managers magnify the weaknesses of people, but should force each person to move constructively by relying on the strengths.

Consequently, encouragement for a good deed takes precedence over punishment for a relatively large mistake or weakness.

Rewards should be fair and related to the individual's performance. Sometimes evaluations are done in such a way that people who do not feel fair do not understand the reason for such behavior. Discrimination in behavior and giving rewards incorrectly are the causes of coldness and indifference of people in work. If a person succeeds in his work, he should be rewarded in such a way that he and others attribute the reason for receiving the reward to his performance and not to other factors and consider him worthy of receiving that reward.

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